

Trends in Textile Effluent Quality and Treatment: A Comparative Analysis of Major Bangladeshi Industrial Hubs

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ABSTRACT:

This study undertakes a comprehensive temporal assessment of textile wastewater quality across key industrial hubs in Bangladesh from 2012 to 2024. Utilizing a systematic review of 29 peer-reviewed studies and employing statistical analysis such as trend analysis, Pearson correlation, and hierarchical cluster analysis, this research evaluates the progression of critical effluent parameters, namely BOD, COD, TDS, TSS, DO, pH, and selected heavy metals including Pb, Cr, Cu, and Zn. Findings reveal persistent exceedance of regulatory limits, with mean COD and BOD levels at 524.6 mg/l and 193.7 mg/l respectively, surpassing Department of Environment, Bangladesh thresholds by over 100%. Although DO improved to 4.6 mg/l in 2024, it remained below acceptable limits in several years. Textile Industrial zones such as Chittagong, and Gazipur demonstrated consistently high contaminants levels. Correlation and Cluster analyses identified strong associations between organic pollutants and salinity indicators. This review underscores the inadequacy of existing treatment practices and advocates for the integration of advanced technologies such as advanced oxidation process and strong regulatory enforcement. The study contributes to the discourse on sustainable industrialization and the necessity of circular economy models in textile wastewater governance.

Keywords: ETP, Wastewater, Sustainability, Heavy materials, TDS

Nomenclature

BOD- Biological Oxygen Demand

COD- Chemical Oxygen Demand

DO- Dissolved Oxygen

TDS- Total Dissolved Solid

TSS- Total Suspended Solids

BDL- Below Detection Limit

ETP- Effluent Treatment Plant

DoE- Department of Environment

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1. Introduction

Bangladesh's textile industry has become a vital sector both nationally and internationally, which significantly impacts the nation's economic framework. The sector is considered the backbone of Bangladesh's economy, contributing over 13% to the nation's GDP and generating more than 84% of total export revenues. The sector ranks as the second-largest garment exporter globally following China, with exports reaching \$43 billion in the fiscal year 2023-2024 [1] anticipated to surpass \$100 billion in export revenue by 2030 [2]. The United States constitutes the primary export market for Bangladeshi garments, with around 21.50% of total exports. The European Union, specifically Italy, Spain, Belgium, Germany, France, and the Netherlands, is the second-largest export market for BD apparel by value [2]. This sector is one of the biggest sources of employment in Bangladesh, offering work to approximately 4.4 million individuals, primarily women, which contributes to social mobility and poverty alleviation [1]. The industry's global importance is underscored by its competitive advantages, such as low labor costs and duty-free market access, making it an appealing location for international brands [3]. The sector advances sustainable development goals by fostering positive employment, gender equality, and economic expansion, serving as a catalyst for Bangladesh's economic transition.

However, the sector's growth has come at a significant environmental cost, particularly in water pollution. The textile industry is a water-intensive sector that exerts significant pressure on global water resources [4]. Water is used at various phases of clothing manufacture, including sizing, scouring, bleaching, dyeing, and printing. Petek et al. [5] and Zheng et al. [6] indicated that around 100-180 liters of water are required to process 1 kilogram of textile product, based on the specific type of procedure employed [7]. The typical finishing and dyeing mill consumes around 150 m³ of water per ton of processed textile. Textile wet processing mills discharge over 80% of industrial wastewater [8,9]. Miah et al. [10] showed that the textile industry in Bangladesh discharged wastewater in 2011, 2015, and 2020, with amounts of 145 million m³, 201 million m³, and 317 million m³, respectively. Projections indicate a 60% annual increase in the global volume of textile waste from 2015 to 2030 [11]. Currently, industries employ several types of dyes to attain the required color quality. In earlier times, natural dye served as the primary agent for coloring textile fabrics. Due to the inefficiency of natural dyes and the rising demand for dyed and printed fabrics, natural dyes alone are inadequate to provide the necessary supply for these products. Therefore, synthetic

dyes have supplanted natural dyes in the market. Technologists have widely adopted synthetic dyes across all domains of textile dyeing and printing. However, the issue is that synthetic dye is highly poisonous and detrimental to the environment. The American Dye Manufacturers Institute (ADMI) reported detecting dye concentrations in wastewater between 1000 and 1500 ADMI units [12]. Various metals, such as Al, Ba, Ni, Fe, Sb, Sr, Cr, Cu, Mn, and Zn, have been documented in textile dye wastewater, surpassing thresholds [13]. The significant volumes of wastewater adversely affect the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of aquatic habitats, posing severe threats to public health, animals, and ecological systems. Textile effluent contributes to health issues or causes diseases, including dermal irritation, respiratory ailments, and central nervous system disorders [14,15].

Despite comprehensive research on textile effluent quality, the existing literature is characterized by limited datasets and a lack of comparative assessments over many years. Most studies concentrate on singular years, particular criteria, or limited industrial areas, yielding valuable but partial perspectives on overarching patterns. Furthermore, there has been insufficient focus on comprehensive measurements, crucial for addressing global environmental issues. This review addresses these gaps by compiling available data and judging how well wastewater treatment methods work, giving a unified view that was missing from earlier studies. Limitations, including data inadequacies for particular years, are recognized.

The objective of this review is to conduct a longitudinal analysis of effluent quality trends within Bangladesh's textile industry, focusing on the major industrial hubs over the past decade (2012-2024). Key parameters such as pH, BOD, COD, DO, TDS, TSS, and heavy metals are analyzed to evaluate temporal trends and disparities.

2. Wastewater Quality Parameters in the Textile Industry

2.1 BOD

BOD is a metric that indicates the amount of oxygen needed to biochemically decompose organic substances in water. After releasing biodegradable organic matter into water, microbes degrade the waste, transforming it into simpler inorganic and organic compounds. This breakdown creates stable and acceptable byproducts like SO₄, CO₂, NO₃, and PO₄. It also lowers the amount of dissolved oxygen in water [16], as shown in equation (i). Under low-oxygen conditions for the aerobic decomposition of waste, a distinct group of microbes

performs anaerobic decomposition, resulting in the production of undesirable byproducts such as NH₃, CH₄, and H₂S, as seen in equation (ii).

2.2 COD

COD is the quantity of oxygen necessary to oxidize organic materials in a water sample using an efficient chemical oxidizing agent. Equation (iii) represents the amount of oxygen, in milligrams, consumed by one liter of the sample when treated with an acidic potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) solution under heat. During COD measurement, organic matter is altered into CO₂ and water, irrespective of whether the substance is biologically assimilable [17,18].

2.3 pH

The pH value indicates the degree of acidity or alkalinity in water and is determined by the concentration of hydrogen ions, as expressed in Equation (iv) [19]. At 25°C, deionized water typically exhibits a neutral pH of 7.0, comparable to that of purified water. Wastewater with a pH greater than 7.0 is considered alkaline. High alkalinity in wastewater can cause significant environmental and ecological risks [20].

$$pH = -\log_{10} [H^+] \quad iv$$

2.4 DO

DO is a water quality parameter that is necessary for the survival of aquatic life, as well as the reproduction, vigor, and development of species [21,22]. Before discharging the effluent into a surface water body, the effluent discharge standard mandates that it must contain 4.5-6.0 mg/l of dissolved oxygen. A study reveals that textile effluent contains 1.95 mg/l - 5.83 mg/l of dissolved oxygen, which is a significant threat to aquatic life [23].

2.5 TSS

TSS refers to the solid constituents of water that remain in suspension. The original size of the solid in suspension post-purification is roughly 0.001 mm, and purification is viable for sizes above 0.001 mm and up to 1 mm. The main pollutants in textile effluent include suspended solids, anions (HCO₃⁻, CO₃²⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₂⁻, Cl⁻), cations (K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺), and organic matter [24,25]. Textile effluents can lead to elevated levels of suspended solids, which may obstruct the respiratory organs of aquatic organisms. The maximum permissible limit of total

suspended solids (TSS) is 20 mg/L for drinking water, 75 mg/L for industrial effluents, and 30 mg/L for finishing water [26,27].

2.6 TDS

The solid content in polluted water is generally classified into two types based on particle size: colloidal and dissolved (soluble) solids. The remaining solid is the dissolved solid consisting of soluble metal salts like Fe²⁺, Ca, Mg, Na, and K [28,29]. TDS is correlated with the salinity and conductivity of water. The assessment of solids in water is crucial for ensuring its safety for consumption [30,31].

2.7 Heavy Metals

A variety of metals are included in the national environmental quality criteria for industrial effluent, including Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni, and Zn, among others. Some metals, typically found in trace amounts in the environment, can be detrimental to humans, plants, fish, and other aquatic organisms [32].

3. Existing Wastewater Treatment Practices and Their Limitations

Existing wastewater treatment commonly involves a combination of physical, chemical, and biological processes, as illustrated in Figure 1 [33]. These processes are designed to remove pollutants, reduce organic matter and dyes, and disinfect the water prior to its discharge into the environment [34]. The preliminary treatment starts by removing large debris and grit that can damage or clog subsequent treatment processes. Screening, grit removal, and coarse solids separation are common techniques used. After that the primary treatment involves sedimentation or settling to remove suspended solids. During this stage, wastewater is held in large tanks where gravity separates the solids from the water. The settled solids, known as primary sludge are then removed for further treatment [33]. The secondary stage primarily focuses on removing dissolved and suspended biological matter. It typically involves biological processes where microorganisms consume organic pollutants. Common methods include activated sludge processes, trickling filters, and oxidation tanks. Activated sludge involves the use of a microbial community to break down organic matter [35]. The wastewater is aerated to promote microbial growth, and the resulting sludge is separated from the treated water [36]. Wastewater is sprayed over a bed of rocks or plastic media, allowing a microbial film to form and degrade the organic pollutants as the water trickles through. Oxidation tanks are large, shallow ponds where sunlight, bacteria, and algae

Figure 1 Wastewater treatment techniques (Created by Napkin AI).

work together to purify the water [35]. Furthermore, the tertiary treatment is used to remove specific pollutants that remain after secondary treatment, such as nutrients (phosphorus and nitrogen), micropollutants, and heavy metals [36,37]. This method includes filtration and activated carbon adsorption. The final stage involves disinfecting the treated wastewater to kill any remaining pathogens. Chlorination, UV irradiation, and ozonation are commonly used disinfection methods [38]. Despite the systematic structure of these stages, it is crucial to assess their practical effectiveness and limitations in real-world scenarios.

However, current methods face several limitations that contribute to persistent high effluent levels despite known aquatic life and human health risks [39,40]. Traditional treatment methods are not designed to remove many emerging contaminants, such as microplastics, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances [41-43]. These compounds are dangerous for the environment, even at low concentrations [42,44]. For instance, microplastic fibers from synthetic textiles, often containing flame retardants like triphenyl phosphate, can accumulate in fish and impact their metabolism [43]. Moreover, many advanced treatment technologies such as membrane bioreactors (MBRs) and advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) offer improved pollutant removal but come with higher capital and operational costs [45,46]. MBRs, while effective, can suffer from membrane fouling, reducing efficiency and increasing energy consumption [47]. AOP, including photocatalysis, show promise for treating recalcitrant pollutants but can be energy-intensive unless driven by solar energy [48]. Consequently, the economic constraints can limit the widespread adoption of these technologies, particularly in developing countries or smaller municipalities [49].

In addition to these technological and economic limitations, wastewater treatment produces sludge, a byproduct containing concentrated pollutants, including heavy metals and pathogens. Improperly managed sludge can cause environmental risks, such as soil and water contamination. While some sludge can be converted into fertilizer, this requires careful management to avoid spreading contaminants [50]. Aging wastewater treatment infrastructure in many regions contributes to treatment inefficiencies. Combined sewer overflows, where domestic sewage mixes with surface runoff, can overload treatment plants during storms, leading to the discharge of untreated wastewater into rivers and coastal waters. Maintaining and upgrading this infrastructure requires substantial investment, often exceeding available resources [51].

Equally important, while many treatment plants are equipped for nitrogen and phosphorus removal, achieving consistently low effluent levels remains difficult [52]. Excess nutrients in water bodies can lead to eutrophication, causing algal blooms and oxygen depletion that harm aquatic ecosystems [53,54]. Factors such as varying influent concentrations, operational inconsistencies, and inadequate system design can compromise nutrient removal efficiency. For example, in prefabricated or compact treatment plants, nutrient excesses can occur due to design limitations, requiring alternative solutions such as increasing dissolved oxygen or using bioaugmentation [52].

Given these multiple challenges, current wastewater treatment targets may be insufficient to protect surface water quality, particularly with increasing socio-economic developments and climate change [55]. Lio et al. suggests that even halving the proportion of untreated wastewater discharged by 2030, as outlined in Sustainable Development Goal 6.3, may not be enough to

ensure adequate water quality [55]. Addressing pollution at the source is often overlooked [50]. So, without effective control measures, treatment plants face an uphill battle in achieving desired effluent quality [56,57].

4. Methodology

A comprehensive literature review establishes a solid basis for the progression of knowledge. This process aids in the development of theories, highlights areas with extensive existing research, and reveals gaps where further investigation is required [58]. The selection of industries for this study was based on a thorough review of academic literature and reports focusing on the textile industrial hubs in Bangladesh, as illustrated in Figure 2. The primary criteria for inclusion were wastewater quality parameters, and timeframes. Additionally, Microsoft Excel, and QGIS were employed for data preparation and study map.

4.1 Sampling and Data Sources

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify and evaluate studies reporting key wastewater quality parameters in the textile industry. Relevant

peer-reviewed articles were retrieved from three databases: PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus. The search strategy employed a combination of keywords to ensure comprehensive coverage of the topic. The keywords used included: (“wastewater treatment” OR “effluent treatment”) AND (“textile industry” OR “textile wastewater”) AND (“BOD” OR “DO” OR “COD” OR “TDS” OR “pH” OR “heavy metals”) AND (“effluent characterization” OR “environmental compliance in Bangladesh”).

The initial yielded a total of 747 articles. Duplicate records were identified and removed using Mendeley reference management software, resulting in 613 unique records. These records were screened based on titles and abstracts to determine their relevance to the textile sector and wastewater quality analysis. At this stage, some articles were excluded for not meeting the predefined eligibility criteria. A total of 125 full-text articles were then assessed for eligibility. Studies that lacked empirical data, focused on non-textile industries, or presented only theoretical modeling without experimental validation were excluded. Following this review, an additional 96 articles were removed. As a result, 29 articles, published between 2012

Figure 2 Geographical distribution of textile industry locations in Bangladesh.

Figure 1 PRISMA flowchart.

Table 1 Average water quality parameters across multiple years.

Year	TDS mg/l	pH mg/l	COD mg/l	BOD mg/l	DO mg/l	TSS mg/l	Cr mg/l	Cu mg/l	Zn mg/l	Pb mg/l	Ref
2012	2052.7	8.5	478.3	174.3	1.6	189.8	0	0.1	3.3	0	[35]
2013	1507.4	8.5	826	324	-	-	-	-	-	1.4	[36,37]
2014	5300.7	9.8	1292.3	439.4	0.5	209.7	-	-	-	-	[38]
2016	1165.3	8.1	98	60	8	530	-	-	-	-	[39,40]
2017	1687.3	8.2	315.6	88.6	3.3	182.2	0.1	0.2	2.9	0.1	[41-43]
2018	2082	7.8	231.8	277.2	-	125.3	-	-	-	-	[44]
2020	602.6	7.5	297.5	14.9	4.5	391.7	0	0	0.1	0.1	[26,45-48]
2021	887.2	8.4	69	-	4.4	-	-	1.1	-	1.1	[49-51]
2023	763	-	1313.7	293.3	-	57.3	-	-	-	-	[52]
2024	2539.2	7.8	323.5	71.6	4.6	281	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	[53-62]
Maximum	5300.7	9.8	1313.7	439.4	4.6	530.0	0.2	1.1	3.3	1.4	
Minimum	602.6	7.5	69.0	14.9	0.5	57.3	0.1	0	0.1	0	
Average	1858.7	8.2	524.57	193.7	3.99	245.8	0.08	0.3	1.6	0.4	
SD	1294.3	0.63	437.72	137.6	2.23	142.2	0.07	0.4	1.6	0.5	
Average ± SD	1858.7 ± 1294.3	8.2 ± 0.63	524.57 ± 437.72	193.7 ± 137.6	3.99 ± 2.23	245.8 ± 142.2	0.08 ± 0.07	0.3 ± 0.4	1.6 ± 1.6	0.4 ± 0.5	
DoE Standards	2100	6.0–9.0	250	50	4.5-8	100	0.50	3.00	5.00	0.10	

and 2024, were deemed relevant and included in the final analysis.

The selection process adhered to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis) guidelines, incorporating the four systematic phases: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion. A detailed account of this process is presented in Figure 3, which outlines the progression and filtering of studies leading to the final **dataset used for the review**.

4.2 Statistical Analysis

Statistical tests like trend analysis, Pearson's correlation, and hierarchical cluster analysis (CA) were used on the data sets to look at the overall quality of effluents and possible sources of different pollutants in the textile industrial area. Descriptive statistics were generated to illustrate the average behaviors and dispersions, including the mean and standard deviation of the parameters. Jupyter Python notebook and Excel were used for statistical analysis of the data.

5. Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarizes mean values of critical wastewater quality parameters from 2012 to 2024, benchmarked against established standards from the DoE Bangladesh. The complete datasets underpinning this analysis are provided as supplementary materials.

5.1 Water Quality Over Time

5.1.1 BOD and COD Trends

Figure 4 illustrates that BOD values reached at 439.4 mg/l in 2014, which indicates considerable organic pollution, and then decreased to a minimum of 14.9 mg/l in 2020, demonstrating improved water quality. The average BOD concentration over the years was 193.7 mg/l, consistently above the DoE's limit of 50 mg/l, signifying recurrent pollution of water bodies by organic pollutants. COD levels exhibited an identical trend, reaching a maximum of 1313.7 mg/l in 2023, far beyond the 250 mg/l standard, with an average of 524.57 mg/l. The notable rises in both BOD and COD from 2012 to 2014 indicate substantial pollution, likely stemming from industrial activities. Both metrics, however, experienced a considerable decline from 2016 to 2017, potentially due to enhanced wastewater treatment or a reduction in pollutant sources. Despite these advancements, the trend line shows that pollution levels in 2023 increased once more, particularly in COD, which remains a concern for compliance with environmental rules.

5.1.2 TDS and TSS Trends

Figure 5 shows that the levels of TDS and TSS change a lot. In several years, both levels have been higher than the DoE limits of 2100 mg/l for TDS and 100 mg/l for TSS. The highest level value of TDS was 5300.7 mg/l in 2014, which showed that there were a lot of dissolved

Figure 4 Annual trend of BOD and COD levels in textile effluents between 2012 and 2024.

Figure 5 Trend in TDS and TSS concentrations in textile effluents from 2012 to 2024.

contaminants in the water. In 2020, however, the level dropped to 602.6 mg/l, which showed that treatments were getting better. Nonetheless, the average TDS concentration persisted at elevated levels, underscoring persistent apprehensions regarding dissolved solids in the water. TSS followed a similar pattern, reaching a high point of 530 mg/l in 2016, thereafter declining to 57.3 mg/l in 2023, suggesting that the way suspended solids are managed may change in the future. Still, the average TSS of 245.7 mg/l implies difficulties in managing suspended contaminants.

Despite some observed improvements, the levels of TDS and TSS continue to raise concerns regarding water quality, suggesting that sustained efforts are required to comply with DoE regulations.

5.1.3 pH and DO Trends

The pH values, ranging from 7.5 to 9.8 predominantly fell within the DoE prescribed range of 6-9, as illustrated in **Figure 6**, showing that the water was mostly alkaline. The all-time high pH value was 9.8

Figure 6 Annual trend of pH and DO concentrations in textile effluents between 2012 and 2024.

Table 2 Pearson Correlation among the wastewater quality parameters

	TDS	pH	COD	BOD	DO	TSS
TDS	1					
pH	0.78022	1				
COD	0.444818	0.809804	1			
BOD	0.585528	0.785675	0.796939	1		
DO	-0.0321	-0.30605	-0.21237	0.294756	1	
TSS	-0.19029	-0.27669	-0.56097	-0.62823	-0.40562	1

recorded in 2014 indicates a potential for elevated alkalinity, which can impact aquatic organisms, particularly if it continues over an extended period [87]. Conversely, the pH decreased to 7.5 in 2020, after which it varied between 7.5 and 8.4, remaining nearer to neutral. In contrast, DO concentrations displayed a concerning trend, plummeting to 0.5 mg/l in 2014, much beneath the DoE suggested range of 4.5-8 mg/l, indicative of subpar water quality and possible hypoxic conditions. The diminished dissolved oxygen levels in 2014 may be associated with heightened

organic pollution or eutrophication. In 2016, there was a noticeable increase in DO levels that generally stabilized at 4.5-4.6 mg/l in 2020, 2021, and 2024, more closely confirming to the DoE standards.

5.2 Pearson Correlation

The Pearson correlation analysis, as presented in **Table 2**, revealed strong positive correlations between pH and several key parameters: total dissolved solids (TDS, $r = 0.78$), chemical oxygen demand (COD, $r = 0.81$), and

Figure 7 Hierarchical cluster analysis based on the wastewater quality parameters.

biochemical oxygen demand (BOD, $r = 0.79$). These correlations indicate a potential link among the alkalinity of the wastewater, the concentration of dissolved particles, and the existence of organic pollutants. There was also a high relationship between COD and BOD ($r = 0.80$), which makes sense because they both come from organic contamination that is often present in textile effluent.

TDS also had a moderate to strong relationship with both pH ($r = 0.78$) and BOD ($r = 0.59$). This means that the amount of dissolved solids may change when organic matter breaks down. On the other hand, TSS had a negative correlation with COD ($r = -0.56$), BOD ($r = -0.63$), and dissolved oxygen (DO, $r = -0.41$). This means that suspended particles could be getting in the way of breaking down organic matter or making it harder for oxygen to move through the effluent. pH ($r = -0.31$) and COD ($r = -0.21$) exhibited moderate negative correlations with DO, while BOD ($r = 0.29$) exhibited a slight relationship with DO. These findings reflect the complex and often non-linear dynamics of oxygen availability in organically enriched aquatic environments. Lastly, the near-zero correlation between TDS and DO ($r = -0.03$) suggests that these parameters are governed by distinct environmental and chemical mechanisms.

5.3 Cluster Analysis

Hierarchical cluster analysis was employed to examine associations among wastewater quality parameters, with the resulting dendrogram presented in **Figure 7**. This approach facilitated the identification of underlying patterns and potential influencing factors within textile effluent datasets. Two distinct clusters emerged: Cluster 1, comprising pH, BOD, DO, and TSS, reflects strong interrelationships among parameters typically indicative of organic pollution and general water quality. Cluster 2 includes COD, TDS, and parameters associated with both organic and inorganic contamination, suggesting differing sources and chemical behaviors.

The Euclidean distance shown on the horizontal axis quantifies the degree of dissimilarity between parameters, with smaller distances indicating greater similarity. In the dendrogram, shorter branch lengths correspond to more closely related parameters, while longer branches represent greater differences. The clustering height visually represents the level of similarity at which parameters are grouped, providing insight into the relationships among wastewater quality indicators. The clear separation between these clusters underscores a distinction between naturally occurring water quality indicators and those primarily linked to industrial discharge. This classification enhances the understanding

of effluent variability and supports the refinement of wastewater treatment strategies and environmental monitoring efforts within the textile sector.

5.4 Highly Contaminated Areas in Bangladesh

The textile industry has contributed significantly to the emergence of severe water pollution hotspots across Bangladesh, with Chittagong, Gazipur, Savar, Narayanganj, and Kashimpur identified as the most critically impacted regions. Notably, Chittagong's effluent parameters have remained persistently high since initial monitoring in 2012, with TDS peaking at 12 570 mg/l that year and maintaining concentrations above 2 500 mg/l through 2017. COD levels exhibited similar persistence, ranging from 1 854.61 mg/l in 2012 to 1 158 mg/l in 2021, consistently exceeding DoE standards by 400 to 700 percent. In contrast, Gazipur demonstrates a clear trend of escalating contamination, as lead concentrations increased from 0.0339 mg/l in 2012 to 2.12 mg/l in 2021. BOD values followed a comparable trajectory, rising from 136 mg/l to 425 mg/l over the same period, representing a 212 percent increase over the decade.

Transitioning to the Savar industrial zone, data indicate a progressive accumulation of heavy metals, with copper concentrations rising from 0.0507 mg/l to 0.69 mg/l. BOD levels similarly increased, from 107.29 mg/l to 197.6 mg/l as of 2023. Furthermore, other industrial zones including Narayanganj, Kashimpur, and Tongi demonstrate parallel patterns of deteriorating water quality. Narayanganj's COD levels rose from 1 011 mg/l in 2013 to 1 275 mg/l in 2018, while Kashimpur recorded persistently elevated chromium levels, consistently around 0.12 mg/l between 2013 and 2017. Tongi's TDS measurements reached 3 140 mg/l in 2017, reflecting a marked increase from previously recorded values.

6. Sustainability Perspective

6.1 Economic Feasibility of ETP Implementation

The economic feasibility of implementing ETPs involves evaluating the costs and benefits associated with wastewater treatment, considering factors such as capital investment, operational expenses, potential revenue streams, and cost savings [88-90]. Several studies focus on the costs associated with different wastewater treatment technologies [88,91,92]. For example, the economic feasibility of water reuse within a polyvinyl chloride plant was examined using an aerobic membrane bioreactor followed by a double pass reverse osmosis process. The study looked at the idea for industrial water treatment, even though the required expenditure was costly at 2.5 million euros [88]. Similarly, the quality and cost of a wastewater

treatment plant were also looked at using the GPS-X and CapdetWorks simulation programs. This shows how important it is to use technical and economic simulation when developing wastewater treatment plants that work well and save money [91]. Studies investigate several types of constructed wetlands, including horizontal flow-constructed wetlands and vertical flow-constructed wetlands, to see if they are economically feasible for decentralised treatment systems [92].

6.2 Global Sustainability Regulations

The rules for managing wastewater treatment around the world are modifying quickly. The transition is happening because people are more worried about water pollution, shortages, and the need for a circular economy [93]. In this context, the European Parliament has approved a resolution on urban wastewater treatment that emphasizes lowering pollutant levels in treated wastewater, especially when it comes to total phosphorus, total nitrogen, and BOD. It is essential to point out the visible effects of these initiatives on the condition of rivers, seas, and lakes throughout the European Union (EU) [94]. Furthermore, several EU regulations influence how urban water pollution is controlled. These directives require every nation to make sure that all water bodies have good ecological and chemical quality [95].

Additionally, the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) is an important policy that sets up a complete system for managing and protecting water in Europe. To follow the WFD, countries involved often need to build or change infrastructure at the local level [96]. The Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) also specifies specific guidelines for how to treat, release, and collect urban wastewater [97]. The EU is also working on new rules to keep an eye on and reduce the amount of active chemicals in treatment plants [98].

However, it should be noted that member states' application of EU discharge guidelines differs. Norway is not a member of the EU, but it follows EU wastewater policy because it is a member of the European Economic Area (EEA). This is especially pertinent for removing phosphorus using chemical treatment methods [97]. On the other hand, nations like Ukraine have different rules for the amount of phosphorus in wastewater than the EU does, which raises the risk of eutrophication in aquatic bodies [99]. Moreover, in Slovenia, discrepancies between national legislation and EU standards in water management raised concerns regarding the implementation of the right to access safe drinking water [100].

Turning to the Asian region, several countries continue to face significant challenges in achieving

Sustainable Development Goals related to wastewater management. For example, in Bangladesh, initiatives are underway to promote sustainable development through improved wastewater management practices [101]. Similarly, China has made considerable progress by integrating wastewater treatment into its broader sustainable development agenda [102]. The country has made substantial investments in wastewater treatment infrastructure and technology to reduce the discharge of untreated effluent [101]. In parallel, policies supporting sustainable energy and green technology have also contributed indirectly to improved water quality through more efficient wastewater management systems [103].

Meanwhile, human resource management practices in Vietnam are evolving to incorporate environmental sustainability considerations [104]. In India, the promotion of the "blue revolution" reflects a national focus on sustainable development to enhance water quality [105]. Compared to other South Asian nations, Sri Lanka is generally regarded as having relatively better water management practices. In this context, addressing corporate social responsibility in Sri Lankan organizations emerges as a critical strategy for advancing environmentally sustainable practices [106].

6.3 Circular Economy in Textile Wastewater Reuse

The circular economy (CE) model offers a sustainable alternative to the traditional linear economy in the textile industry, particularly concerning wastewater reuse. The linear model, characterized by "take–make–use–dispose," exacerbates environmental impact, whereas the CE model emphasizes reducing, reusing, and recycling to keep resources in a closed loop [107,108]. In the context of textile wastewater, CE principles aim to minimize water consumption, recover valuable resources from wastewater, and reuse treated wastewater for various purposes [109]. The circular economy in the textile industry is deeply connected with sustainable development. It requires balanced coordination among technological, economic, environmental, and social aspects [110]. The core strategies for eco-friendly processing of textile products are governed by the "3Rs": Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle [111].

Water is vital across different stages of the apparel manufacturing, making its sustainable management crucial. This sector implementing CE principles in the water and wastewater for more sustainable management [112]. Water reuse from wastewater treatment is a transition towards a circular economy [113].

7. Conclusion and Recommendation

Bangladesh, as a developing nation, relies heavily on industrial expansion to sustain its economic growth, with the textile sector serving as the primary contributor to foreign currency earnings and employment. However, this rapid industrialization has come at a significant environmental cost. The discharge of untreated or insufficiently treated textile effluents, laden with organic pollutants, heavy metals, and inorganic salts, has severely degraded the quality of surrounding water bodies, rendering them unfit for domestic, agricultural, or industrial use.

This study revealed that concentrations of COD (up to 1313.7 mg/L), BOD (up to 439.4 mg/L), TSS (up to 530 mg/L), and Pb (up to 1.4 mg/L) frequently exceeded national standards, indicating ineffective treatment across many industrial zones. Although parameters such as TDS, DO, pH, Cu, Zn, and Cr occasionally aligned with regulatory thresholds, persistent exceedances in critical pollutants underscore systemic inefficiencies in existing effluent treatment practices.

To address these challenges, it is imperative that industries adopt advanced treatment technologies, particularly Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs), membrane bioreactors, and nutrient recovery systems. Moreover, the government must enforce stringent compliance monitoring, incentivize the adoption of circular economy models, and invest in upgrading treatment infrastructure. Lessons from international best practices should inform policy reforms, ensuring that environmental protection is not compromised in pursuit of industrial growth.

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Conflict Interests

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